

Coordinated Offloading: Meta-Guided Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning for Edge-Cloud Continuum

Muhammad Rafid[†], Vasilis Avgerinos[†], Kostas Ramantas[‡], Christos Verikoukis, Senior Member, IEEE^{†*}

[†] *ISI/ATHINA RC, 26504 Patra, Greece (e-mail: {mrafid, avgerinos, cveri}@isi.gr)*

[†] *University of Patras, 26504 Patra, Greece*

[‡] *Iquadrat Informatica S. L., Barcelona, Spain, (email: kramantas@iquadrat.com)*

Abstract—The increasing demand for intelligent and low-latency services in edge-cloud continuum systems poses new challenges for dynamic and efficient task offloading. In this paper, we propose a meta-guided multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) framework for distributed task offloading under partial observability. The problem is formulated as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), a solution where each device independently learns an optimal policy under partially observable system states. To address the lack of global coordination in decentralized settings, a lightweight meta-controller is introduced to observe system-level metrics and periodically broadcast a utility signal. This signal is incorporated via reward shaping to guide agent learning without introducing additional communication overhead. The proposed method offers a promising direction for achieving balanced decision-making and scalable coordination in complex edge-cloud environments.

Index Terms—6G networks, Task offloading, Edge-Cloud Continuum, Multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL), Distributed optimization.

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